

Studies in Oxadiazoles. Part V: Synthesis of Some Amido (or Imido) Methyl Derivatives of 2-Amino/Mercapto-5-Aryl-1,3,4-Oxadiazoles as Potential Fungicides

H. SINGH* and L. D. S. YADAV**

Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, Gorakhpur, U.P.

Manuscript received 12 February 1977, accepted 4 July 1977

Several 2-amido (or imido) methylamino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (III) and 3-amido (or imido) methyl-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (IV) have been prepared by condensing amide/imide with 2-hydroxymethylamino-1,3,4-oxdiazoles (I) and 3-hydroxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (II), respectively. Eighteen of these compounds have been compared with Dithane M-45, a commercial fungicide, in their fungitoxicity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus*, and most of these have exhibited fungicidal activity in the same range as Dithane M-45 at 1000 ppm.

THE systemically active oxathlin fungicides require an aryl amide substituent for their enhanced activity¹ and the cyclic imide portion of several fungicides, like captan, folpet, difolatan and cycloheximide, has been suggested to be the toxic moiety²⁻⁴. The 2-amino/mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazoles and their derivatives have been reported to possess pesticidal activities⁵⁻¹¹, and that no amido/imidomethyl oxadiazole of the type III or IV has apparently been reported so far. In view of above, it was presumed that the oxadiazole compounds (III and IV) with aryl amide/cyclic imide moieties might be fungicides of choice.

2-Amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been prepared according to the method of Gibson¹¹ by oxidative cyclisation of aldehyde semicarbazone with bromine and anhyd. sodium acetate. The 5-aryl-2-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were prepared by the method of Young and Wood¹². 2-Hydroxymethylamino-oxadiazoles (I)

TABLE I—5-ARYL-2-HYDROXYMETHYLAMINO-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES (I)

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	m. p. °C	Mol. formula	Found	C(%)		Found	H(%)	
						Calcd	Calcd		Calcd	Calcd
1	H	72	171	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$	56.32	56.54	4.89	4.71		
2	<i>o</i> -Chloro	65	165	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$	48.12	47.89	3.41	3.55		
3	<i>p</i> -Chloro	70	190	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$	47.96	47.89	3.62	3.55		
4	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	68	186	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$	54.06	54.30	5.24	4.98		
5	<i>p</i> -Nitro	61	179	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$	45.91	45.76	3.67	3.39		

* For correspondence,

** Chemistry Department, M. G. Degree College, Gorakhpur, U.P.

were prepared¹⁸ by the action of formaldehyde on 2-aminooxadiazoles, and similarly, 3-hydroxymethyl-oxadiazole-2-thiones (II) were obtained from the 2-mercapto-oxadiazoles. The condensation of compounds I with amide/imide in concd. H₄SO₄ gave III. On similar treatment II gave the compounds IV. The structures of the compounds were supported by IR data.

Experimental

S-Aryl-2-hydroxymethylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (I) were prepared by heating appropriate 2-aminooxadiazole (0.1 M) and formaldehyde (0.1 M, 8.1 ml of 37% soln.) in DMF (20 ml) on water bath for 30-45 min. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured into water, filtered, the solid was washed with water for several

TABLE 2—5-ARYL-3-HYDROXYMETHYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLE-2-THIONES (II)

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	m. p. °C	Mol. formula	N(%)		S(%)	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1	H	74	149	C ₉ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	13.64	13.46	15.44	15.38
2	<i>o</i> -Chloro	61	139	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	11.41	11.55	12.97	13.20
3	<i>p</i> -Chloro	73	147	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	11.32	11.55	13.06	13.20
4	<i>m</i> -Methyl	59	170	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.91	12.61	14.15	14.41
5	<i>p</i> -Methyl	62	181	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.43	12.61	14.03	14.41

TABLE 3A—2-AMIDO (OR IMIDO) METHYLAMINO-5-ARYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES (III)

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	m. p. °C	Mol. formula	C(%)		H(%)		
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
<i>R</i> ₁ = Benzamido									
1	H	70	182	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	65.04	65.31	4.63	4.76	
2	<i>o</i> -Chloro	61	173	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	58.21	58.45	4.18	3.96	
3 ^a	<i>p</i> -Chloro	74	203	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	58.09	58.45	3.85	3.96	
4	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	72	192	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	63.21	62.96	5.06	4.94	
5	<i>p</i> -Nitro	63	176	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄	56.49	56.64	3.64	3.83	
<i>R</i> ₁ = Nicotinamido									
6 ^b	H	65	187	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂	60.86	61.02	4.21	4.41	
7	<i>o</i> -Chloro	56	162	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂ Cl	54.41	54.63	3.60	3.64	
8	<i>p</i> -Chloro	70	205	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂ Cl	54.34	54.63	3.43	3.64	
9	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	62	195	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂	60.13	59.08	4.74	4.62	
10	<i>p</i> -Nitro	52	182	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₆ O ₄	52.63	52.94	3.61	3.53	
<i>R</i> ₁ = Phthalimido									
11 ^c	H	76	233	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂	63.96	63.75	3.86	3.75	
12	<i>o</i> -Chloro	66	209	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	57.31	57.54	3.06	3.10	
13	<i>p</i> -Chloro	79	241	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	57.86	57.54	3.31	3.10	
14	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	72	201	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	61.42	61.71	3.85	4.00	
15	<i>p</i> -Nitro	61	196	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₂	56.13	55.89	3.09	3.01	

Significant bands (cm⁻¹) in IR spectra (in KBr)

	C=N,	C-O-C,	C=O,	Amino/amido, N-H	Substituted benzene/ pyridine nucleus
a.	1630	1027	1685	3348	1602, 1480, 860
b.	1626	1030	1653	3350	1587, 1493, 770, 685
c.	1637	1050	1733	3355	1605, 1464, 715

times and recrystallised from ethanol to give the desired product. The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

5-Aryl-3-hydroxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (II)—The appropriate 2-mercaptooxadiazole (0.1 M) was dissolved in a minimum quantity of ethanol and formaldehyde (0.1 M, 8.1 ml of 37% soln.) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 1.5 hr, cooled, poured into water, filtered and the crude product was recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 2.

2-Amido (or imido) methylamino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (III)—The compound I (0.03 M) and amide/imide (0.03 M) were dissolved in a minimum quantity of concd. H_2SO_4 (75 ml) under cooling and stirred

for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice, the residue filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. The compound; III thus prepared are recorded in Table 3A.

3-Amido (or imido) methyl-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (IV) were prepared from compound II exactly in the same manner as the compound III from I. The compounds are recorded in Table 3B.

Fungicidal Screening The test organisms were *A. niger* and *A. flavus*. The antifungal activity was evaluated by agar-plate technique^{14,15} at three concentrations viz. 1000 ppm, 100 ppm, and 10 ppm and the number of replications in each case was three. A commercial fungicide *Dithane M-45* was tested under

TABLE 3B—3-AMIDO (OR IMIDO) METHYL-5-ARYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLE-2-THIONES (IV)

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	m. p. °C	Mol. formula	N(%)		S(%)		
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
<i>R₁ = Benzamido</i>									
16 ^a	H	71	170	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	13.41	13.50	10.06	10.29	
17	<i>o</i> -Chloro	59	96	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	12.23	12.16	9.49	9.26	
18	<i>p</i> -Chloro	65	104	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	12.01	12.16	9.53	9.26	
19	<i>m</i> -Methyl	68	116	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.63	12.92	9.64	9.85	
20	<i>p</i> -Methyl	70	140	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.74	12.92	9.71	9.85	
<i>R₁ = Nicotinamido</i>									
21	H	65	181	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	17.61	17.95	10.29	10.26	
22	<i>o</i> -Chloro	64	106	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	16.36	16.16	9.43	9.24	
23 ^b	<i>p</i> -Chloro	68	132	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	16.50	16.16	9.01	9.24	
24	<i>m</i> -Methyl	70	111	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	16.91	17.18	10.04	9.82	
25	<i>p</i> -Methyl	72	121	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	17.34	17.18	9.56	9.82	
<i>R₁ = Phthalimido</i>									
26	H	71	162	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.11	12.46	9.56	9.50	
27	<i>o</i> -Chloro	64	78	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	11.03	11.31	8.38	8.61	
28 ^c	<i>p</i> -Chloro	78	89	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	11.62	11.31	8.83	8.61	
29	<i>m</i> -Methyl	66	108	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	13.31	13.33	9.84	10.16	
30	<i>p</i> -Methyl	74	130	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	13.66	13.33	10.03	10.16	

Significant bands (cm⁻¹) in IR spectra (in KBr)

	C=N,	C-O-C	C=O,	Amido, N-H	C=S,	Substituted benzene/pyridine nucleus		
a.	1625	1045	1660	3320	1332	1600,	1485,	680
b.	1613	1053	1667	3300	1330	1493,	837,	687
c.	1635	1040	1735	—	1320	1605,	1500,	860

TABLE 4—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING

Compound Serial as in Tables 3A & 3B	Average Percentage Inhibition after 96 Hours					
	Organism— <i>A. niger</i> , Concentrations used			Organism— <i>A. flavus</i> , Concentrations used		
	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
1	51.6	30.4	18.3	52.7	29.2	19.7
2	59.3	31.8	17.4	59.6	32.7	16.9
3	80.1	35.5	19.2	78.3	36.2	17.5
7	62.5	34.6	18.3	60.8	30.4	13.9
8	90.6	45.3	28.2	86.4	41.3	23.4
9	92.1	44.6	29.9	85.7	38.0	21.3
11	62.2	28.7	13.8	63.4	27.9	15.7
13	96.1	49.2	30.5	98.2	51.3	29.8
14	100	70.7	56.2	100	76.4	59.0
16	60.5	28.3	9.8	56.3	21.7	7.3
17	69.8	31.6	11.9	71.4	30.8	15.1
18	98.5	60.3	32.0	81.9	51.4	29.2
22	71.7	37.8	21.5	62.3	33.0	17.6
23	100	78.9	55.4	100	75.3	53.1
24	56.5	29.6	17.0	50.7	23.9	8.8
26	58.6	30.3	19.2	59.1	29.4	17.6
28	100	80.4	64.1	100	76.6	58.5
29	59.9	33.7	23.9	56.0	30.7	19.3
<i>Dithane M-45</i>						
(A commercial fungicide)						
	100	86.0	71.2	95.3	80.6	65.9

similar conditions. The percentage inhibition by various compounds is recorded in Table 4.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{(C-T) \times 100}{C}$$

where, C = Diameter of fungus colony in control plates after 96 hours.

T = Diameter of fungus colony in treated plates after 96 hours.

Results and Discussion

The compound Nos. 3, 8, 9, 13, 14, 18, 23 and 28 exhibited the fungicidal activity almost in the same range as the commercial fungicide at 1000 ppm. The compound serial 14, 23 and 28 inhibited 100% the growth of both the fungal species at 1000 ppm, and appear to be more potent than the commercial fungicide against *A. flavus* at this concentration. It is noteworthy

that in all such compounds chloro or methoxy group in aryl moiety appears to enhance the fungitoxicity considerably, and that the introduction of chloro group at *para* position is more effective as compared to *ortho* position.

The compounds IV were more active than the compounds III having similar substituents. This might be attributed to the presence of C=O and C=S groups in the compounds IV, as it has been observed earlier¹⁶ that the combination of C=O and C=S groups sometimes works better than either alone. Further, the compounds IV contain -N-C=S linkage which is a possible toxophore in many pesticides^{17,18}.

The phthalimide compounds were more potent than their benzamido and nicotinamido analogues; this might be due to the presence of one additional C=O group¹⁶ in the former. However, these results indicate that there is the following order of fungitoxicity in the

amido/imido derivatives :

phthalimido > nicotinamido > benzamido.

The most active compound serial 14, 23 and 28 inhibit >50% the growth of both the test fungi even at 10 ppm, hence appear to be promising fungicides.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. R. P. Rastogi, Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, for providing necessary facilities and Dr. J. S. Yadav, B.H.U., Varanasi for recording IR and elemental analyses. Thanks are also due to U.G.C., New Delhi, for providing financial assistance to one of them (L. D. S. Y.) to carry out this work.

References

1. B. VEN SCHMELING and M. KULKA, *Science*, 1966, 152, 819.
2. R. J. LUKENS and J. G. HORSFALL, *Phytopathology*, 1967, 57, 876.
3. R. J. LUKENS and J. G. HORSFALL, *Phytopathology*, 1962, 52, 925.
4. J.G. HORSFALL, "Principles of fungicidal action," p. 279, Waltham (Mass.), Chronica Botanica Company, 1956.
5. I. SAIKAWA and T. MAEDA, Japan. 70 08, 861 (1970), *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, 73, 14855.
6. Y. OKADA, Japan, 7024, 982 (1970); *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, 73, 98953.
7. G. S. REDDIN, U. S., 3, 608, 082 (1971); *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, 75, 151803.
8. H. SINGH and L. D. S. YADAV, *Indian J Chem.*, 1976, 14B, 711.
9. H. SINGH and L. D. S. YADAV, *Agr. Biol. Chem.*, 1976, 40(4), 759.
10. S. GIRI, H. SINGH and L. D. S. YADAV, *Agr. Biol. Chem.*, 1976, 40(1), 17.
11. M. S. GIBSON, *Tetra'edron*, 1962 18, 1377.
12. R. W. YOUNG and K. H. WOOD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 400.
13. I. HIRAO, R. UENO and Y. KATO, Japan. 70 08, 977 (1970); *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, 73, 14856.
14. U. S. D. A. Circular No. 198, (1931).
15. J. G. HORSFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1945, 11, 357.
16. J. G. HORSFALL and S. RICH, *Contrib. Boyce Thompson Inst.* 1951, 16, 361.
17. R. L. METCALF, "Organic Insecticides," Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1955, p. 106.
18. M. C. GOLDSWORTHY, E.L. GREEN and M. A. SMITH, *J. Agr. Research*, 1943, 66, 277.